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2 **Rangeland Ecology and Management**

3
4 SUPPLEMENTAL TABLES AND FIGURES

5
6 Non-target Woody Plant Responses to Broadcast Herbicide Treatment for Mesquite and
7 Pricklypear Control

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9 R. J. Ansley, M. Clayton and W. E. Pinchak

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15 **Table S1.** Tolerance categories and shrub injury level descriptions for each category.
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Code and Color	Category	Calculated Tolerance Rating	General Observation of Stand-Level Species Response
HT	Highly Tolerant	80-100	Very few long-term negative effects; < 5% canopy reduction; <1% mortality
T	Tolerant	60-79.9	Minimal long-term negative effects; generally <25% canopy reduction and <5% mortality.
MT	Moderately Tolerant	40-59.9	Moderate long-term negative effects; 25-50% canopy reduction and <25% mortality.
MS	Moderately Susceptible	20-39.9	Substantial long-term negative effects; generally 50-75% canopy reduction; potentially moderate (25-50%) mortality, but not in all cases.
S	Susceptible	0-19.9	Very high long-term negative effects; generally >75% canopy reduction; potentially high (>50%) mortality, but not in all cases.

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Table S2. Relative wildlife value ranking of selected plant species in Central Texas (Linex 2014).

Common Name	Scientific Name	Family	Value Ranking
Algerita	<i>Mahonia trifoliolata</i>	Berberidaceae	Good-Fair
Bois d'arc (Osage Orange)	<i>Maclura pomifera</i>	Moraceae	Good-Fair
Bumelia	<i>Bumelia lanuginosa</i>	Sapotaceae	Excellent
Buttonbush	<i>Cephalanthus occidentalis</i>	Rubiaceae	Fair
Catclaw Acacia	<i>Acacia greggii</i>	Fabaceae	Good-Fair
Croton, Texas	<i>Croton texensis</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Fair
Elm, American	<i>Ulmus americana</i>	Ulmaceae	Excellent
Elm, Cedar	<i>Ulmus crassifolia</i>	Ulmaceae	Excellent
Elm, Winged	<i>Ulmus alata</i>	Ulmaceae	Good
Ephedra	<i>Ephedra antispyhilitica</i>	Ephedraceae	Good
Fourwing saltbrush	<i>Atriplex canescens</i>	Chenopodiaceae	Excellent
Hackberry, Netleaf	<i>Celtis laevigata</i>	Ulmaceae	Good
Hawthorn	<i>Crataegus mollis</i>	Rosaceae	Excellent
Juniper (Young)	<i>Juniperus pinchotii</i>	Cupressaceae	Poor
Liveoak	<i>Quercus virginiana</i>	Fagaceae	Good-Fair
Lotebush	<i>Zizyphus obtusifolia</i>	Rhamnaceae	Good
Pecan (native)	<i>Carya illinioensis</i>	Juglandaceae	Good-Fair
Persimmon	<i>Diospyros virginiana</i>	Ebenaceae	Good-Fair
Plum, Mexican	<i>Prunus mexicana</i>	Rosaceae	Good
Pricklyash	<i>Zanthoxylum hirsutum</i>	Rutaceae	Fair-Poor
Pricklypear	<i>Opuntia spp</i>	Cactaceae	Good-Fair
Soapberry, Western	<i>Sapindus saponaria</i>	Sapindaceae	Good
Sumac, Littleleaf	<i>Rhus microphylla</i>	Anacardiaceae	Good
Sumac, Skunkbush	<i>Rhus aromatica</i>	Anacardiaceae	Good
Tasajillo	<i>Opuntia leptocaulis</i>	Cactaceae	Fair
Whitebrush	<i>Aloysia gratissima</i>	Verbenaceae	Poor
Wolfberry	<i>Lycium berlandieri</i>	Solanaceae	Fair-Poor
Yucca	<i>Yucca spp</i>	Liliaceae	Fair-Poor

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Linex, R.J. 2014. Range plants of North Central Texas – A land user’s guide to their identification, value and management. USDA-NRCS Publication, Weatherford, TX. 345 pp.

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 27 **Table S3.** *P*-values for PROC MIXED analysis of mesquite and lotebush root-kill (RK), canopy
 28 reduction (CR) and tolerance rating (TLR) as affected by site (Vernon vs Hamlin), herbicide
 29 treatment (TRT), spray year (YEAR; 2 levels, 2013 and 2014) and years post-treatment (YPT).
 30 Any *P*-value < 0.05 that includes site as an effect is shown highlighted in gray with bold text. Df
 31 = degrees of freedom.

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Effect	Df	RK	CR	TLR
-----Mesquite-----				
SITE	1	0.0497	0.8207	0.2900
TRT	3	0.0017	0.0006	0.0146
YEAR	1	<.0001	<.0001	0.0084
YPT	1	0.0877	0.5275	0.4291
SITE*TRT	3	0.1680	0.9922	0.6196
SITE*YEAR	1	0.1442	0.9724	0.4291
SITE*YPT	1	0.0434	0.0294	0.0576
TRT*YEAR	3	0.0002	0.0003	0.0139
TRT*YPT	3	0.7313	0.9504	0.4321
YEAR*YPT	1	0.3673	0.2851	0.2900
SITE*TRT*YEAR	3	0.0391	0.3464	0.3904
SITE*TRT*YPT	3	0.7163	0.3575	0.3401
TRT*YEAR*YPT	3	0.9940	0.5612	0.2504
SITE*TRT*YEAR*YPT	4	0.5375	0.7782	0.6196
-----Lotebush-----				
SITE	1	0.9740	0.0026	0.0013
TRT	3	0.4713	0.0084	0.0086
YEAR	1	0.3746	0.0017	0.0034
YPT	1	0.9428	0.0210	0.0466
SITE*TRT	3	0.9277	0.2867	0.3627
SITE*YEAR	1	0.5538	0.0309	0.0096
SITE*YPT	1	0.0828	0.0607	0.0555
TRT*YEAR	3	0.6591	0.5894	0.5289
TRT*YPT	3	0.4233	0.6147	0.6559
YEAR*YPT	1	0.0314	<.0001	<.0001
SITE*TRT*YEAR	3	0.4881	0.1070	0.1833
SITE*TRT*YPT	3	0.7412	0.3873	0.6025
TRT*YEAR*YPT	3	0.4818	0.0684	0.0916
SITE*TRT*YEAR*YPT	4	0.7412	0.9424	0.9357

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Table S4. *P*-values for PROC MIXED analysis of mesquite and lotebush root-kill (RK), canopy reduction (CR) and tolerance rating (TLR) as affected by site (Vernon vs Baird), herbicide treatment (TRT), and years post-treatment (YPT) after the 2015 spray year. Any *P*-value < 0.05 that includes site as an effect is shown highlighted in gray with bold text. Df = degrees of freedom.

Effect	Df	RK	CR	TLR
-----Mesquite-----				
SITE	1	0.0002	<.0001	<.0001
TRT	3	0.0002	<.0001	<.0001
YPT	1	0.4227	0.0482	0.0129
SITE*TRT	3	0.0275	<.0001	<.0001
SITE*YPT	1	0.3728	0.5871	0.1475
TRT*YPT	3	0.6051	0.0287	0.0026
SITE*TRT*YPT	3	0.9675	0.3816	0.0430
-----Lotebush-----				
SITE	1	0.0313	0.0027	0.0036
TRT	3	0.3532	0.4194	0.2326
YPT	1	0.1619	0.3049	0.4163
SITE*TRT	3	0.4062	0.2379	0.1862
SITE*YPT	1	0.4827	0.4720	0.3946
TRT*YPT	3	0.5927	0.4010	0.4115
SITE*TRT*YPT	3	0.9778	0.5415	0.4337

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Figure S1. Monthly precipitation at the Hamlin site compared to 30-year average, 2010-2017.

Treatment spray events are shown in July 2013 and 2014.

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Figure S2. Monthly precipitation at the Baird site compared to 30-year average, 2010-2017.

Treatment spray event is shown in July 2015.

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 62 Figure S3. Mesquite tolerance rating to 4 treatments at 3 months, 1 year and 2 years post-
 63 treatment after 3 different spray years. Tolerance color code is on right panel: Blue = highly
 64 tolerant (80-100), green = tolerant (60-79.9), yellow = moderately tolerant (40-59.9), orange =
 65 moderately susceptible (20-39.9), red = susceptible (0-19.9). Treatment codes: CA =
 66 clopyralid+aminopyralid; CA+Tr = CA+triclopyr; CA+Pc = CA+picloram; Cp+Tr =
 67 clopyralid+triclopyr.

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 71 Figure S4. Pricklypear tolerance rating to 4 treatments at 3 months, 1 year and 2 years post-
 72 treatment after 3 different spray years. Ancillary information is in Figure S3 caption.
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 76 Figure S5. Lotebush tolerance rating to 4 treatments at 3 months, 1 year and 2 years post-
 77 treatment after 3 different spray years. Ancillary information is in Figure S3 caption.

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 82 Figure S6. Hackberry tolerance rating to 4 treatments at 3 months, 1 year and 2 years post-
 83 treatment after 3 different spray years. Ancillary information is in Figure S3 caption.

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